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STORE PATRONAGE AND CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN DISCOUNT STORES- AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Retail has been an important contributor to a nation's GDP, especially for the developing nations where the purchasing power of the people is largely affected by the format of retail and the pricing decisions of the retailers. Discount retail is an integral part of retail across the world and likewise in India also. Discount stores which were simply dump yards for factory seconds a few years ago have emerged as a new business opportunity for Indian retailers. These stores no longer stock export surplus rejects but offer a great value proposition to the savvy, price sensitive Indian customer's ambience, service and overall shopping experience. This paper documents the importance of store patronage and examines how a discount store can gain customer loyalty. It highlights the impact of loyalty programs on store patronage and brings forth the factors related to store convenience and employee's attention on image of the store.

Key Words: Patronage, Brand Awareness, Loyalty, Store Attribute, Discount, Store Convenience

1.0 Introduction:

The discount retail industry in India is taking off with enthusiasm as it provides consumers with luxury within their budget. Discount retailing, a post-war phenomenon, is an established market practice in countries like the US. However, the concept is new to India because till recently, MRP was the 'be all' end as far as pricing was concerned. In the West, discount stores were conceived to serve consumer needs of baby-boomer families. As the retail industry is booming in India, shoppers are faced with sales, discount and price-offs, which are not only pleasing to their eyes but also to their wallets. Bargains are always appealing, particularly to the regular working Indian consumers who do not want a hole in pockets by the month-end. Consumers tend to be thrifty shoppers and bargain hunters and hence get drawn to discount retail chains. Designed to operate with low-price mark-ups and basic service levels, these formats achieved higher sales volumes and faster merchandise turnover. This pricing strategy enabled the likes of Wal-Mart, Kmart and Target to have a wide presence in the US within a short span of time. Deals, freebies and bargains have refined shopping experiences in these countries and now the same tactic is being deployed across retail formats in India. There are various avatars of discount retailing emerging in the country. While first movers like Subhiksha have pioneered EDLP or everyday low pricing, some others like Brand Factory (part of the Future Group) and Mega mart (part of Arvind Mills) have taken the concept of factory outlets to a new level. While some others like Big Bazaar launched its 'Sabse Saste 3 Din' offer. Mega mart outlets have designated 'market place zones' within the store where non-moving merchandise is accumulated and offered at a discounted price. Moreover, this zone is located at strategic areas so that they catch the eye of the discount seeking consumer. Therefore, it can be seen that the competition is increasing in the discount retail sector and stores are vying to attract the customers and gain their patronage by offering various loyalty programs. This paper analyses the store patronizing behaviour of the customers in the light of loyalty programs offered by the stores. It also documents the impact of brand awareness and brand association on store patronage. The paper also highlights factors related to store convenience and store employee's personal attention on image of the store.

1.1 Review of Literature: While discount retailing is fastest growing segment in retail worldwide, the next decade in organized retail in India will be dominated by it. Nearly 20 per cent to 25 per cent of revenues of most

brands come from discount sales. Keeping in view the importance of discount retail and the value that it is adding to both the consuming and the manufacturing society of India, there is a need to undertake a study on the same. As several players are trying to prove their worth in the market and luring the consumers with many programs and schemes, it is relation to such programs and how they patronize these stores. Therefore, this study can be reasoned in the light of above consideration.

Different authors have recognized that overall image of the store is dependent upon different store attributes. Lindquist (1974) combined models from 19 studies and came up with nine different elements: merchandise, service, clientele, physical facilities, comfort, promotion, store atmosphere, institutional and post transaction satisfaction. Doyle and Fenwick (1974) identified only five elements: product, price, assortment, styling and location. Bearden (1978) concluded upon the following characteristics: price, quality of merchandise, assortment, atmosphere, location, parking facilities and friendly personnel. While Bloemer and Shroeder (2002) opined that store image is a construct of store attributes as perceived by the consumer which is developed through the experiences of the customer with the store. Solgaard and Hansen (2003), in their study concluded that assortment was found to be the single most important driver for the choice between store formats; price level and distance also being important drivers for consumers' choice between store formats. A research by Singh and Powell (2002) stated that quality is considered to be the most important factor followed by price.

Empirical studies suggest that price, as a determinant of satisfaction, varies by store format. (Cox and Cox (1990) found that overall price image of a store affects store choice. Moreover, advertised reference prices can help to create a low overall store price image. Desai and Talukdar (2003) stated that price has implications for store patronage, and strategic decisions related to selecting a target customer base and creating in-store environments. Jacoby and Mazurski (1984) stated that brands and especially store brands have a great importance in the formation of store image and can help project a lower price image for retailer. Simester (1995) concluded that a discount retailer can credibly signal its low costs for other products by advertising prices of selected items. Sieder and Costley (1994) found price to be a major determinant of store choice in the grocery shopping context. They also reported that consumers had accurate perceptions of market pricing related to the store that they considered in their study. According to Yavas (2003), price is an important driver in store choice among a battery of patronage motivations.

Anjali Panda (2013) commented that Indian retail is witnessing a tremendous growth with the changing demographics and increase in income and quality of life of urban people. The study found the patronage behaviour of the customers towards traditional and modern food and grocery retailers. The primary data was collected from a sample of consumers visiting both organised and unorganized outlets in Odisha state. It was concluded that an understanding of the patronage behaviour helps the modern retailers to focus and strengthen the elements of their retail offerings which is more valued by customers.

Subhashini Kaul (2006) stated store loyalty is the most initial variable of interest to retailers. The paper reviewed existing retail literature and identified the dimensions of store loyalty; with specific focus on its antecedents such as store image. It also discussed methodological issues in measuring store loyalty and image in the current Indian context.

Wornchanok Chaiyasoonthorn and Watanyoo Suksa-ngiam (2011) opined that discount stores, hypermarkets, and supermarkets have been dominating the retail industry in Thailand for a long time. Their research investigated the factors affecting Thai customers purchasing goods and services from such types of retail stores in Bangkok, Thailand. 424 respondents were selected from 4 areas in Bangkok; correlations and multiple regressions statistical analyses were employed to estimate relationships between independent and dependent variables. The results showed that factors correlated with purchase of goods and services from modern retail stores were distance from home, distance from workplace, purchase intention, customer satisfaction, perceived service quality, personal income, and household income. However, when considered with significant factors and multicollinearity, only three factors: distance from workplace, purchase intention, and personal income could be used to create a predicting equation.

Yasmin Hassan Nik Maheran Nik Muhammad, Hatinah Abu Bakar (2010) in their paper submitted that knowledge on furniture consumers' retail patronage will promote and enhance efforts to increase sales at furniture stores and could guide future research. The research developed a general model of retail patronage and to empirically test the relationships proposed in the model in the context of furniture market. It reviewed the existing retail patronage models, developed a general framework of retail patronage behaviour and tested a model in furniture store shopping patterns. Based on a review of the literature the study proposed to adapt Darden's patronage model of consumer behavior. 115 data were collected through survey questionnaires and the underlying relationship among the variables that characterize consumers' patronage behavior towards furniture was studied. Statistically it was found that in terms of shopping orientation, the apathetic shopper and the personalizing shopper was influenced by the lifestyle of the consumer and hence influenced the customer patronage. Store image on the other hand was found to enhance the impact on consumer patronage of the furniture store and moreover acted as both the predictor and the moderator

1.2 Objectives:

- To analyse the impact of store awareness and store choice on store patronage.
- To analyse the factors that lead to store patronage and customer loyalty.
- To examine the attractiveness of discount and satisfaction of the customers with low prices offered by the store

1.3 Hypotheses:

H1: There is a relationship between the awareness about discount and attractiveness of discount.

H2: There is a significant difference between the satisfaction level of male and female customers of the discount store in relation to low prices offered by the store.

H3: Store awareness and store choice have an impact on store patronage.

1.4 Research Methodology: It is an empirical paper, wherein data is collected from 500 respondents across 5 discount stores in Hyderabad, India. Purposive sampling is applied to choose only discount stores and 100 customers are chosen from each store.

1.4.1 **Data Sources:** Primary data is collected from consumers to administer questionnaire. While secondary data is collected from books, magazines, journals, web sites, reports and other sources.

1.4.2 **Questionnaire:** The questionnaire consists of 20 questions with a Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.77.

1.4.3 **Data Analysis Technique:** Data is analysed using Chi-Square test, ANOVA, Regression test and Factor Analysis besides simple ratios and percentages.

2.0 Findings: Data was collected regarding the products that are usually bought by the respondents from the discount store. The following table gives details regarding the same.

Table 1.0 Products bought from discount store

Particulars	Number of respondents
Furniture and home furnishing	150
Food and Beverages	400
Hardware equipment and home supplies	120
Clothes	350
Craft and hobby items	20
Sporting goods	100
Books and music	17

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

It can be seen that popular products that are usually bought by customers from the discount store are food and beverages, clothes, home furnishings, hardware equipment and home supplies. Respondents were also asked if they bought vouchers to avail the discount. 52% (260) respondents said that they did not buy vouchers to avail the discount but they made use of the loyalty card given by the store while the remaining 48% (240) respondents bought vouchers to avail the discount.

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between the awareness about discount and attractiveness of discount. Data was collected from the respondents about their awareness of the discount and attractiveness of the discount. Chi-Square test was applied to analyse the data and test the hypothesis.

Table 2.0 Test Statistics for Hypothesis 1

	Awareness and attractiveness of discount
Chi-Square	45.7369
df	1
Asymp Sig.	0.01

(Source: Primary data analysis and interpretation)

The chi-square test reveals a statistic of 45.7369. The P value is 0.01. The result is significant at $p < 0.05$. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the awareness about discount and attractiveness of discount. Thus, it can be said that discount stores have to strategize their awareness creation about the discounts that they offer so as to attract the customers to their stores.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant difference between the satisfaction level of male and female customers of the discount store in relation to low prices offered by the store. Chi-Square test was applied to find the difference in the satisfaction among men and women shoppers. The results are presented in table 3.0 below.

Table 3.0 Test Statistics for Hypothesis 2

	Gender-wise Satisfaction of low prices
Chi-Square	19.6078
df	1
Asymp Sig.	0.5

(Source: Primary data analysis and interpretation)

It can be seen (see appendix, table 3.1) that satisfaction is more among female for low price when compared to satisfaction level of male shoppers regarding low prices. The Chi-Square statistic as computed is 19.6078 and P value is 0.5 which means that the hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is a significant difference between the satisfaction level of male and female customers of the discount store in relation to low prices offered by the store. Thus, it can be suggested that, these stores can offer more lucrative discount schemes for products used by female customers and promote their stores popularity by applying special customer promotion tools such as sweepstakes, rewards and rebates especially for women. On the other hand, it can also be recommended that, apart from discounts being offered, these stores can have separate schemes for male customers, which will enhance their satisfaction.

An objective of the study was to examine the factors that lead to store patronage and customer loyalty. Factor analysis was applied and 16 components were narrowed down to 4 components comprising of 12 factors. The analysis is presented in the following table 4.0 as follows:

Table 4.0 Factor Analysis for store patronage and loyalty

Component	Factors in the component	Factor Loading	Percentage Variation (from rotation sums of squared loading)
Component I Loyalty Program	Accepts loyalty card	7.75	18.49
	Feel of being a regular customer	5.38	
	Prefer loyalty program over low prices	5.36	
Component II Personal Attention	Prompt response	7.44	27.19
	Willing to help	7.02	
	Handle Complaints efficiently	6.67	
	Have Neat Appearance	6.06	
Component III Store Convenience	Provides Value for Money	7.45	24.15
	Household items	7.39	
	Best Cafeteria	9.31	
Component IV Store Layout	Feel Safe in the Store	6.07	12.92
	Easy to Locate Items	6.85	
Total Percent Variation from rotation sums of squared loadings			82.75

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

As is seen from table 4.0 above, it can be concluded that attention given by store employees and store convenience has the highest factor loading followed by loyalty program and store layout. Acceptance of loyalty card (7.75), store providing value-for-money spent by the customer (7.45), willingness to help on the part of the employees (7.02), prompt response (7.44) and a good cafeteria (9.31) are among the top factors that impact patronage and loyalty. [See appendix, table 4.1 for KMO Barlett Test Statistic).

Hypothesis 3: Store awareness and store choice have an impact on store patronage.

This hypothesis is tested using ANOVA. ANOVA table determines if the differences between condition means are significant. Results of ANOVA will infer the conclusion about whether the independent variable (store awareness and choice) has an effect on the dependent variable (store patronage). Each variable, as shown in table 5.0 is analysed. [See appendix, table 5.1 for frequencies of each variable)

Table 5.0 ANOVA Statistics for Hypothesis 3

Variables		Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F value	Significance
Remember Slogan/Motto	Between	29.50	9.83	2.19	.45
	Within	4.50	4.50		
	Total	34.00			
Familiar with the store	Between	126.00	42.00	5.25	.31
	Within	8.00	8.00		
	Total	134.0			
Familiar with places inside the store	Between	129.5	43.17	.30	.84
	Within	144.5	144.50		
	Total	274.00			
Remember colour	Between	56.00	18.67	.19	.89
	Within	98.00	98.00		
	Total	154.00			
Remember Logo	Between	86.00	28.67	.29	.84
	Within	98.00	98.00		
	Total	184.00			
Remember Uniform	Between	93.50	31.17	.37	.80
	Within	84.50	84.50		
	Total	178.00			

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

As depicted in the table 5.0, the Sig. value in all cases such as remember slogan, logo, colour, uniform and familiarity with the store is greater than .05, thus null hypothesis is accepted and it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean i.e., store awareness and choice does not have any impact on store patronage.

It can be seen (see appendix, table 6.0), that most of the respondents pay special attention to the offers because they possess loyalty card and they enjoy participating in the loyalty and savings program and most of them opined that a loyalty program do not offer them attractive benefits. Some of the respondents felt that the registration systems of loyalty programs infringe upon their privacy.

It is revealed in table 7.0 (see appendix. table 7.0), that aspects of patronage also support third hypothesis i.e., store choice does not has any impact on store patronage. As is seen in the table, out of 500 customers 260 state that their choice of store will not lead to patronizing behaviour, whereas 120 customers have neutral opinion, also provide equal probability to be added in favour of the hypothesis. Although major determinants of patronage to the store depends upon ambiance and discount offered in the store. As shown from results in the table 7.0, discount offers prove lucrative for customers to spend more on their next visit as results show that out of 500 customers, 320 customers intended to spend more than their previous visit to the store, and 380 customers are attracted towards ambiance of the store. Customer patronage to the store is also affected by merchandise available in the store

Regression is applied in order to test the impact of customer loyalty on store patronage.

Table 8.0 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.099	.010	.008

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

The above table 8.0, tests the level of relationship between store patronage behaviour (dependent factor) and customer loyalty (independent factor). It can be seen the value of R square is 0.010 that is 1 percent of variance of store patronage behaviour is explained by customer loyalty, though this values is very low due to other situation and factors which would be having high impact on customers' store patronage.

Table 8.1 Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	42.396	.993		42.692	.000
	Customer Loyalty	.190	.086	.099	1.856	.064

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

The regression test is further validated and it is seen whether the test was significant or not, coefficients are computed and it is seen that probability .064 is attained, which is higher than 0.05, therefore, it can be concluded that customer loyalty does not have impact on store patronage behaviour.

As the study is on discount store, price sensitivity is a factor considered by the store to attract and retain customers. However, as tests above yield that loyalty does not impact patronage, the test is revalidated with inclusion of lucrative offers under the loyalty program and therefore the result shows remarkable difference which is explained by applying regression test as under.

Table 8.2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.919 ^a	.845	.845

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

Table 8.3 Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.452	.667		20.153	.000
	Customer Loyalty	2.005	.038	.919	52.181	.000

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

From the table model summary it can be seen that the value of R square is highly increased, showing 84.5 percent of variance and the p value is .001 which is less than .05. It can be concluded from the results that customer loyalty is explaining high variance and has a significant impact on store patronage. Therefore, if stores provide lucrative offers to loyalty card holders, there is a significant change in their patronizing behaviour and also increase in store footfall.

3.0 Major Conclusions of the Study: From the study, it can be concluded that discount stores are liked by many customers and store can pay more attention on re-designing the loyalty program and make it easy to use the loyalty card. Employees being an important component in the store customers got good experience when responded promptly were willing to help and handled complaints immediately by understanding customers' specific needs. It was observed that Store layout also has an important role in attracting the consumers and the layout decisions facilitated easy identification of products and shelves. It is also seen that discounts offered were in the range of 10-15% on food and beverages, upto30% on clothes and 20-30% on household items. Discount stores have to strategize their awareness creation about the discounts that they offer so as to attract the customers to their stores. It is also concluded that male and female customers react differently to the discounts offered. Therefore, apart from low prices other schemes can also be offered by the store to attract and retain male and female customers. Apart from discounts being offered, these stores can have separate schemes for male customers, which will enhance their satisfaction. The study also concludes that store awareness and choice does not have an impact on patronage and hence these stores must initiate loyalty programs that would encourage patronizing behaviour of the customers. It is also concluded from this study that some of the factors that will enhance store patronage and loyalty are store layout, convenience in the store, availability of merchandise, prompt service by the employees and value for money spent. It can be concluded that choice and patronage of the store vary across formats of retail. What applies to a discount store need not necessarily apply to a hypermarket or a departmental store. This paper has highlighted the patronage and loyalty for a discount store. Scope lies in undertaking further research in this area for other retail formats. Lucrative offers on loyalty card changes to a remarkable extent the impact on store patronage and helps the store to retain existing customers and also attract new customers.

4.0 Suggestions from the Study: It is suggested to that these stores can have fresh stock of food and beverages along with other products such as health and personal care products, books and music, craft and hobby items. It is suggested that loyal customers (membership customers) should be sent sequent communication about low prices and offers so as to help them avail such things technology aids such as email, SMS can be used for such communication. It is suggested that the stores can have visually appealing physical facilities clean, attractive and well placed materials such as bags, catalogs, etc. and the transactions should be error free. To attract the customers back to the store, it should handle complaints, returns and exchanges strategically. It is suggested that the store should keep a stock of all the items regularly needed by the customers by adopting effective replacement techniques. It is also recommended that the store should advertise all its special sales and discounts.

Through this study, it is also suggested that the various elements that design a brand such as slogan, logo and uniform of the employees should be incorporated in promoting the store. Care must be taken in designing the elements that create store awareness and enhance the possibility of a prospective customer getting attracted to the store and existing customer becoming loyal to the store. Stores should also concentrate on offering lucrative schemes because these schemes being included in the loyalty program enhances the patronizing behaviour.

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Appendices

Table 2.1 Frequencies for awareness and attractiveness of discount

	Attractiveness of discount	Non attractiveness of discount
Awareness about discount	430	70
Non Awareness about discount	340	160

(Source: Primary data analysis and interpretation)

Table 3.1 Frequencies for Gender-wise satisfaction of low prices

	Satisfied with low prices	Unsatisfied with low prices
Male	210	290
Female	280	220

(Source: Primary data analysis and interpretation)

Table 4.1 Test Statistics for Factor Analysis- KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.970
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3.188
	Df	406
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Primary data analysis and interpretation)

Table 5.1 Frequencies for variables of Store awareness and Store choice

Particulars	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Remember the slogan on motto of discount store.	37	43	115	120	185
Familiar with the store	80	67	153	110	90
Familiar with places inside the store	100	60	81	130	129
Remember the color of discount store.	104	63	72	146	115
Remember the logo of store well.	76	64	108	114	138
Remember the uniform of the employees of the store.	64	89	73	142	132

(Source: Primary data analysis and interpretation)

Table 6.0 Opinion about Loyalty program of the store (1- Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4- Agree, 5- Strongly Agree- scale applies to both table 6.0 and 7.0)

Particulars	1	2	3	4	5
Having a loyal card make me feel like a regular customer.	80	210	90	80	40
I prefer loyalty program over lower prices.	90	200	90	80	40
I enjoy participation in loyalty and saving program.	90	190	90	70	60
Loyalty and saving program offers attractive benefits.	100	150	100	90	60
I am paying more attention on special offers because of loyalty card.	110	190	60	70	70
The registration systems of loyalty programs infringe on my privacy.	90	190	90	80	50

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)

Table 7.0 Aspects of Store patronage

Particulars	1	2	3	4	5
This store is my first choice when I intend to buy something	120	60	40	180	100
The physical facilities at the store are visually appealing.	50	70	150	100	130
I intend to buy items worth more than Rs 5000 in the next visit	40	85	100	100	175
The store has clean, attractive and convenient public areas (restrooms, fitting rooms).	45	50	50	205	150
I intend to visit more than 5 times in the next month	20	10	150	140	180
When the store promises to do something by a certain time, it will do so.	50	60	140	150	100
The store has never disappointed me	70	30	200	150	50
The store has merchandise available when the customers want it.	50	80	120	100	150
The store insists on error-free sales transactions and records.	100	70	130	50	150
Employees in the store have the knowledge to answer customers' questions.	120	140	40	150	50
In one visit I can get all those products I want from this store	130	160	70	50	90
I will recommend the store to others	170	60	160	70	40
The store willingly handles returns and exchanges.	60	70	90	120	160

(Source: Primary Data analysis and interpretation)